

1 **Kinase and phosphatase inhibition as a signal transduction-centric approach to adjunctive**
2 **chemotherapies for the treatment of gynecologic cancers: PLK4.**

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7 Men and women differ in large part resulting from the presence or absence of gynecologic organs
8 including the ovaries, the uterus, the lining of which is known as the endometrium, and the entry to the
9 uterus (womb), the cervix (1), all of which are targets for development of malignancies (2-7); vulvar
10 cancer is less common (8). Cancer, or unrestricted cell division which develops into a tumor after
11 remaining unchecked, evades active cell death and cell cycle control mechanisms, sustaining its survival
12 through growth factor signals (9) which are transduced to the nucleus to activate and repress transcription
13 of genes (10, 11). These signals are transduced between the plasma membrane and the nucleus by the
14 action of kinases and phosphatases, enzymes that utilize conformational changes and a catalytic site to
15 translate a signal from the extracellular environment to a change in gene expression. Catalytic sites are
16 pharmacologically targetable, and small molecule targeting of the appropriate kinase or phosphatase target
17 will disrupt or block this transduction (12, 13). We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (14, 15) to
18 identify and validate kinase and phosphatase targets in gynecologic oncology, including cancer of the
19 cervix. Here we describe a differentially expressed, up-regulated, and catalytically available kinase target
20 in cervical cancer: PLK4.

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27 **Keywords:** kinase, phosphatase, signal transduction, gynecologic oncology, therapeutic targets in cancer,
28 chemical biology, systems biology of human cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), the proteome (total collection of proteins in the cell) and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of human cancer (16-20). This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - cancer subtypes, like adeno and squamous forms of non-small cell lung cancer, metastasis to distant sites, including the lymph nodes, the lungs, the liver, the brain, and bones, and the circulating tumor stem cell, which emerges from the primary tumor, disseminates through the body and establishes a novel entity in a separate organ (21-26).

Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), administered in combination with FDA approved broad-spectrum chemotherapeutics like CDK4/6 inhibitors, and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies (27, 28) to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities, fully augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe a kinase therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the cervical cancer transcriptome: a kinase target that is up-regulated and catalytically available: PLK4.

Results

Figure 1: PLK4 is differentially expressed in cervical cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the cervix from humans with cervical cancer.

n=5 normal cervical tissue

n=5 primary tumors (cervix; human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
204887_s_at	0.00023773	-5.5241679	0.91121	-1.9176479	PLK4	115/22277	99.5

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal cervical tissue and in primary tumors of humans with cervical cancer (14), we discovered differential expression of polo-like kinase 4, encoded by *PLK4* in cervical cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of PLK4 changed more than 99% of the human cervical tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22277 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PLK4 messenger RNA in cervical tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of PLK4 during transformation of the cervix.

II. Primary tumors of the cervix from humans with cervical cancer.

n=22 normal cervical tissue

n=20 primary tumors (cervix; human)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1789123	9.14e-09	-7.17	10.028113	-1.62	PLK4	235/42670	99.4

1 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of humans with
2 cervical cancer relative to normal cervical tissue, in a second microarray dataset (15) from independent
3 investigators, we validated differential expression of PLK4 in cervical cancer in humans (**Chart 2**). The
4 expression of PLK4 here changed more than 99% of the human cervical cancer transcriptome when
5 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 42,670 transcripts (“Rank”).
6 Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PLK4 messenger RNA in cervical tumors,
7 demonstrating up-regulation of PLK4 during transformation of the cervix.

8 Thus, differential and increased expression of PLK4 defines the transcriptional landscape of cervical
9 cancer in humans.

10 **Discussion**

11 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
12 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy). Small
13 molecule inhibitors of PLK4 kinase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be tested for
14 efficacy in patients with cervical cancer, with the goal of identifying the most effective kinase inhibitors
15 for management of gynecologic malignancies. An approach that combines kinase and phosphatase
16 targeting with a recently described multi-catalytic strategy that targets dNTP synthesis, replication of the
17 daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, likely delivered in conjunction with standard
18 chemotherapies and drug resistance pump inhibitors in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective
19 in limiting tumor clone resistance and disease (29).

References

1. Hacker, N.F., Gambone, J.C. and Hobel, C.J., 2015. *Hacker & Moore's essentials of obstetrics and gynecology*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
2. Matulonis, U.A., Sood, A.K., Fallowfield, L., Howitt, B.E., Sehouli, J. and Karlan, B.Y., 2016. Ovarian cancer. *Nature reviews Disease primers*, 2(1), pp.1-22.
3. Veneziani, A.C., Gonzalez-Ochoa, E., Alqaisi, H., Madariaga, A., Bhat, G., Rouzbahman, M., Sneha, S. and Oza, A.M., 2023. Heterogeneity and treatment landscape of ovarian carcinoma. *Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology*, 20(12), pp.820-842.
4. Makker, V., MacKay, H., Ray-Coquard, I., Levine, D.A., Westin, S.N., Aoki, D. and Oaknin, A., 2021. Endometrial cancer. *Nature reviews Disease primers*, 7(1), p.88.
5. Urlick, M.E. and Bell, D.W., 2019. Clinical actionability of molecular targets in endometrial cancer. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 19(9), pp.510-521.
6. Frazer, I.H., 2004. Prevention of cervical cancer through papillomavirus vaccination. *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 4(1), pp.46-55.
7. Alfaro, K., Maza, M., Cremer, M., Masch, R. and Soler, M., 2021. Removing global barriers to cervical cancer prevention and moving towards elimination. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 21(10), pp.607-608.
8. Li, Z., Liu, P., Wang, Z., Zhang, Z., Chen, Z., Chu, R., Li, G., Han, Q., Zhao, Y., Li, L. and Miao, J., 2023. Prevalence of human papillomavirus DNA and p16INK4a positivity in vulvar cancer and vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Oncology*, 24(4), pp.403-414
9. Hanahan, D. and Weinberg, R.A., 2000. The hallmarks of cancer. *cell*, 100(1), pp.57-70.
10. Zhang, J., Yang, P.L. and Gray, N.S., 2009. Targeting cancer with small molecule kinase inhibitors. *Nature reviews cancer*, 9(1), pp.28-39.
11. Vainonen, J.P., Momeny, M. and Westermarck, J., 2021. Druggable cancer phosphatases. *Science translational medicine*, 13(588), p.eabe2967.
12. Brivanlou, A.H. and Darnell Jr, J.E., 2002. Signal transduction and the control of gene expression. *Science*, 295(5556), pp.813-818.
13. Sever, R. and Brugge, J.S., 2015. Signal transduction in cancer. *Cold Spring Harbor perspectives in medicine*, 5(4), p.a006098.
14. Pappa, K.I., Polyzos, A., Jacob-Hirsch, J., Amariglio, N., Vlachos, G.D., Loutradis, D. and Anagnou, N.P., 2015. Profiling of discrete gynecological cancers reveals novel transcriptional modules and common features shared by other cancer types and embryonic stem cells. *PLoS one*, 10(11), p.e0142229.
15. Sharma, S., Mandal, P., Sadhukhan, T., Roy Chowdhury, R., Ranjan Mondal, N., Chakravarty, B., Chatterjee, T., Roy, S. and Sengupta, S., 2015. Bridging links between long noncoding RNA HOTAIR and HPV oncoprotein E7 in cervical cancer pathogenesis. *Scientific reports*, 5(1), p.11724.
16. Kirschner, M.W., 2005. The meaning of systems biology. *Cell*, 121(4), pp.503-504.
17. Gehlenborg, N., O'donoghue, S.I., Baliga, N.S., Goesmann, A., Hibbs, M.A., Kitano, H., Kohlbacher, O., Neuweger, H., Schneider, R., Tenenbaum, D. and Gavin, A.C., 2010. Visualization of omics data for systems biology. *Nature methods*, 7(Suppl 3), pp.S56-S68.
18. Fitzgerald, J.B., Schoeberl, B., Nielsen, U.B. and Sorger, P.K., 2006. Systems biology and combination therapy in the quest for clinical efficacy. *Nature chemical biology*, 2(9), pp.458-466.
19. Butcher, E.C., Berg, E.L. and Kunkel, E.J., 2004. Systems biology in drug discovery. *Nature biotechnology*, 22(10), pp.1253-1259.
20. Dey, S.S., Kester, L., Spanjaard, B., Bienko, M. and Van Oudenaarden, A., 2015. Integrated genome and transcriptome sequencing of the same cell. *Nature biotechnology*, 33(3), pp.285-289.
21. Eliyahu, D., Raz, A., Gruss, P., Givol, D. and Oren, M., 1984. Participation of p53 cellular tumour antigen in transformation of normal embryonic cells. *Nature*, 312(5995), pp.646-649.
22. Sims, A.H., Howell, A., Howell, S.J. and Clarke, R.B., 2007. Origins of breast cancer subtypes and therapeutic implications. *Nature Clinical Practice Oncology*, 4(9), pp.516-525.

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23. Chaffer, C.L. and Weinberg, R.A., 2011. A perspective on cancer cell metastasis. *science*, 331(6024), pp.1559-1564.

24. Reya, T., Morrison, S.J., Clarke, M.F. and Weissman, I.L., 2001. Stem cells, cancer, and cancer stem cells. *nature*, 414(6859), pp.105-111.

25. Batlle, E. and Clevers, H., 2017. Cancer stem cells revisited. *Nature medicine*, 23(10), pp.1124-1134.

26. Kreso, A. and Dick, J.E., 2014. Evolution of the cancer stem cell model. *Cell stem cell*, 14(3), pp.275-291.

27. Koike-Yusa, H., Li, Y., Tan, E.P., Velasco-Herrera, M.D.C. and Yusa, K., 2014. Genome-wide recessive genetic screening in mammalian cells with a lentiviral CRISPR-guide RNA library. *Nature biotechnology*, 32(3), pp.267-273.

28. Shah, A.N., Davey, C.F., Whitebirch, A.C., Miller, A.C. and Moens, C.B., 2015. Rapid reverse genetic screening using CRISPR in zebrafish. *Nature methods*, 12(6), pp.535-540.

29. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

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Methods

We utilized GSE63678 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in primary tumors from humans with cervical cancer, as compared to normal cervix (along with GSE67522 for target validation) using microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).